

Propolis extract and their compounds: A review from antiparasitic properties

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Abstract

Propolis is a bee product that has been used in medicine since ancient civilizations. Currently, through several studies, its anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-tumor and immunomodulatory activities are consolidated. However, the field of parasitology remains little explored, especially in relation to helminths. The purpose of this review is to survey the results obtained with propolis around the world and human parasites. Regarding the protozoa, the studies carried out with the protozoa *Trypanosoma* sp. and *Leishmania* sp .; which obtained promising results *in vitro* and *in vivo*. However, studies against *Plasmodium* sp., the etiological agent of malaria, remain shallow. As for helminths, even fewer studies have been carried out, dividing them between *Fasciola* sp. and *Schistosoma* sp. Despite the favorable *in vitro* results with propolis, helminth assays need to be further investigated. However, propolis has shown itself to be a promising natural product when it comes to parasitology, thus opening new paths and approaches in its activity against protozoa and helminths.

Keywords: Antiparasitic, helminths, propolis, protozoa.

1. Introduction

Propolis is a bee product whose medicinal property has been known and used by mankind since centuries ago. Hieroglyphics of bees were widely used by the ancient Egyptians who already made use of propolis in mummification processes, copying in a certain way the activity of bees to embalm dead organisms in their hives in order to protect them against infections (1,2). Greeks and Romans used propolis in the preparation of perfumes, for the relief of pain and in the extraction of foreign bodies from the skin. It is believed that Hippocrates, considered the "father of medicine", employed propolis to heal wounds and ulcers (3). Arabs and Persians, in turn, applied propolis in the extraction of blackheads and as a remedy against myalgia, eczema and rheumatism. It was during the European Renaissance period that the interest in the medicines and treatment used by the ancient people was resumed, thus enabling the return of studies with propolis, which continue to the present day (3).

Known as "the city guardian" (from greek *pro* = entrance and *polis* = city) (4), propolis is a resinous compound produced by honey bees (*Apis mellifera*), being characterized by the complex mixture of botanical exudates collected by the bees from leaves, floral buds and other plant tissues and mixed with pollen, wax, enzymes and saliva of the bees themselves (5–7). Because of its use as a sealant for cracks and holes in the hive propolis also receives the name of "bee glue" being fundamental in maintaining the humidity and temperature of the hive, as well as protecting it against the entry of intruder organisms, embalming dead invaders and maintaining aseptic conditions in place (8–10).

Due to its recurrent use in folk medicine as a potent antibiotic, propolis has been studied in order to better elucidate its complex chemical composition and the its biological activities (11,12). Rich in polyphenols and flavonoids, propolis has an antioxidant activity widely described in the literature (13–15). It also stands out its anti-inflammatory (16–20), immunomodulator (21–26), antiviral (27,28), antimicrobial (29,30), anticancer (22,31,32) potentials, its ability to accelerate tissue regeneration (33,34) and its antiparasitic activity, described in this review (**Figures 1 and 2**).

Figure 1. Overview of the anti-helminthic activity of propolis worldwide and the helminths evaluated.

2. Geographic origins and chemical composition of propolis (Mário)

It is known that the chemical composition of propolis and its various classifications are closely dependent on its geographical origin and botanical source (**Table 1**), since bees choose different plants as a source depending on their habitat (35). It is also noted that the different samples of propolis always present a biological activity, but this biological action is the result of a totally different chemical composition according to their geographic and climatic region of origin (36,37).

Propolis *in natura*, in general, is composed of resins and vegetable balms (40% - 60%), wax (20% - 40%), aromatic essential oils (10%), pollen (5%), minerals (2%) and other compounds (6,37,38). Both its chemical composition and its color (greenish-yellow, green, dark brown and red) vary according to its botanical source and the geographic region where it was collected (39,40).

Table 1. Geographic origin, botanical source and main bioactive compounds from different propolis worldwide.

Geographic origin	Botanical source	Bioactive compounds	References
Brazil (green propolis)	<i>Baccharis dracunculifolia</i>	Prenylated cinnamic acids and flavonoids	(41)
Brazil (red propolis)	<i>Dalbergia ecastophyllum</i> and <i>Symphonia globulifera</i>	Mainly isoflavonoids (formononetin, vestitol, neovestitol and daidzein) and chalcones	(42,43)
Brazil (propolis marrom)	<i>Hyptis divaricate</i> e <i>Populus spp.</i>	Prenylated benzophenone and flavonoids	(8)
Brazil (organic southern propolis)	Poplar trees (<i>Populus</i> L., <i>Salicaceae</i> Family)	Phenolic acids, prenylated derivative of cinnamic acid and flavonoids	(8,44)
Europe, Asia, North America and New Zealand	<i>Populus</i> sp., mainly <i>Populus nigra</i>	Phenolic acids, flavonoids and caffeic acid phenethyl ester (CAPE).	(45–47)
Sonoran Desert (Arizona)	<i>Ambrosia deltoidea</i> , <i>Encelia farinose</i> and <i>Populus</i> sp.	Flavonoid aglycones,	(48)
Cuba and Venezuela	<i>Clusia minor</i> and <i>C. major</i>	Benzophenones derivatives	(49–51)
Russia (birsh propolis)	<i>Betula verrucosa</i> Ehrh.	Flavones and flavonols	(37)
Turkey, Greek and Argelia	<i>Populus</i> sp.	Pinocembrin, pinobanksin and caffeic acid prenylated esters.	(52)
Subtropical Mediterranean	<i>Cupressus sempervirens</i>	Diterpenes	(53)
Hungary	<i>Betula</i> , <i>Populus</i> , <i>Pinus</i> , <i>Prunus</i> , <i>Acacia</i> spp, <i>Aesculus hypocastane</i>	Unknow	(6,54)
Ecuador	<i>Dalechampia</i> spp e <i>Clusia</i> spp	Flavonoids, terpenoids e caffeic acid esters	(6,55)
Hawaiian Islands	<i>Plumeria acuminata</i> e <i>P. acutifolia</i>	Unknow	(6)
Poland	<i>Betula</i> e <i>Alnus</i>	Unknow	(6)

The bioactive compounds present in propolis are directly linked to the botanical source from which the resin was removed, so that the secondary metabolics of the different botanical sources and their consequent geographic regions, as well as the period/season in which they were collected, will interfere in the chemical characterization of propolis (10,37,56,57). Its chemical composition is complex, being rich in polyphenols, flavonoids, aromatic acids,

aliphatic acids, lignans, stilbenes, tannins, terpenes, polysaccharides and aldehydes (58), also occurring the presence of magnesium, iodine, calcium, sodium, potassium, zinc, manganese, iron and copper, as well as vitamins B1, B2, B6, C and E (39).

Patel (32), through analyses performed in HPLC-MS and ULPC-MS elucidate the main bioactive chemical components of propolis, especially chrysin, artepellin C, galangina, quercetina and kaempferol (flavonoids); CAPE (an ester of caffeic acid), nemorosona a (a benzophenone), cardanol and cardol (phenolic lipids) and p-coumaric acid (phenolic acid).. These data corroborate Volpi's study (12) which identified twelve different flavonoids (pinocembrin, acacetin, crisin, rutin, catequin, naringenin, galangin, luteolin, kaempferol, apigenin, miricetin and quercetin), two phenolic acids (scintillate acid and caffeic acid) and one derivative of stilbene (resveratrol).

Due its chemical complexity, propolis cannot be used directly, needing to be purified through the use of suitable solvents in order to extract the inert material and preserve the compounds of interest (59), having water, methanol, ethanol, chloroform, dichloromethane, ether and acetone as the solvents most used in extraction (4). Among these, the use of ethanol stands out for being a solvent capable of producing a propolis extract rich in bioactive compounds, mainly polyphenols, and with low wax content (60). Overall, the choice of the appropriate solvent is based on the target of the study in which the extract will be used (5).

Figure 2. Overview of the antiparasitic activity of propolis worldwide and the protozoas evaluated.

3. Brazilian propolis

The wide application of propolis to prevent and treat colds and other diseases has attracted attention to its chemical composition. Previous studies on the chemical composition and botanical origin of propolis revealed the presence of chemical components belonging to the flavonoids, terpenes, and phenolics (61). In this sense, the Brazilian Propolis, the witch it is found in several regions of Brazil show different chemical composition, depending on the geographical location. Among the studies with the various types of propolis, studies conducted with Brazilian propolis stand out. Brazil is a country rich in biodiversity, which causes a different composition and characterization of propolis according to the region where it is produced and thirteen different classes of propolis are already known (41).

The propolis from Brazil was classified in types according to its origin, chemical composition, and source plant as: green propolis, red propolis and brown propolis among the

main. Among these thirteen types, three stand out in the country: brown propolis, with varied plant and geographical origin; red propolis, extracted mainly in the northeast region and produced from the reddish resin of the *Dalbergia ecastophyllum* (L) Taub tree (30,43) and the green propolis produced in the southeast region, mainly in the Cerrado biome, with the “alecrim-do-campo” (*Baccharis dracunculifolia*) as a botanical source (62,63).

The chemical composition of green propolis is of the high amounts of phenolic compounds. The main chemical classes present in green propolis are flavonoids, phenolics, and aromatic compounds (**Figure 3**), such as p-coumaric acid (**1**), artepillin C (**2**), baccarin (**3**), drupanine (**4**), caffeic acid (**5**), kaempferide (**6**), isosakuranetina (**7**), diidrokaempferide (**8**), aromadendrine (**9**) and caffeoylquinic derivatives (**10-12**). The high concentration of artepillin C, present in green propolis adds more value to resin. The artepillin C (**1**) is responsible for many biological activities reported in the literature. The main volatile compounds found in Brazilian green are sesquiterpenes, such as: (E) -nerolidol, β -karyophyllene, spatulenol and δ -cadinene, which are mainly responsible for the characteristic aroma of green propolis and are also responsible for many biological activities (64).

The Brazilian red propolis has attracted wide attention because to be a new type of propolis that present numerous biological effects, such as: cytotoxic against various tumor cell lines, antibacterial, antifungal, anticariogenic, antioxidant, antiproliferative and anti-inflammatory, among others (65,66). Several researchers identified many compounds in red propolis, the its chemical compounds identified (**Figure 3**), such as: elemicin (**13**), isoelemicin (**14**), methyl isoeugenol (**15**), formononetin (**16**), pinocembrin (**17**), isoliquiritigenin (**18**), liquiritigenin (**19**), medicarpine (**20**), homopterocarpan (**21**), quercetin (**22**) and vestitol (**23**). The isoflavones are considered to be its chemical markers due to their high concentrations in red propolis (64,65). The polyprenylated benzophenones guttiferone E (**24**), xanthochimol (**25**) and oblongifoline A (**26**) are obtained of Lipophilic extract from red propolis. Red propolis also contains some volatile oils, terpenes, however these compounds not to contribute as significantly to biological effects of propolis. The red propolis has this color due to the presence of isoflavans retusapurpurins A (**27**) and B (**28**) in the resin of *Dalbergia ecastophyllum*, botanical source of this propolis (67).

Among the green and red propolis, the brown propolis it features more lipophilic nature of the constituents. Some terpenoids were identified in the extract of brown propolis. The main compounds identified in brown propolis (**Figure 3**) are: isocupressic acid (**29**), acetyl isocupressic acid (**30**), imbricatoloic acid (**31**), communic acid (**32**) and phenylpropanoids derivatives (**33-34**) (68,69). The brown color is characteristic of propolis from different places

and, although many chemical compounds present in this product have already been identified, as well as numerous of its biological effects have already been described, this type of propolis has not been well studied as red propolis it's green. As to the botanical origin, the brown propolis may originate from araucarias. In the southeast, it may originate from species of *Eucalyptus* sp. and other species reported as *Morus alba* (white mulberry), not yet studied.

Many methods of the isolation have been used for isolated of propolis constituents. However different compounds have been identified in different extracts of propolis. The method of extraction and solvent used to obtain the crude extract can change the chemical composition of propolis extract. Therefore, the scientific community's interest in the chemical composition of propolis is continuous, since it can n different biological activities in different extracts (11,69,70).

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|------------------------|-------------------------|-------------------------|---------------------|--|
| (1) R ₁ = H | R ₂ = H | R ₃ = H | R ₄ = OH | |
| (2) R ₁ = H | R ₂ = prenyl | R ₃ = prenyl | R ₄ = OH | |
| (3) R ₁ = H | R ₂ = prenyl | R ₃ = H | R ₄ = | |
| (4) R ₁ = H | R ₂ = prenyl | R ₃ = H | R ₄ = OH | |
| (5) R ₁ = H | R ₂ = H | R ₃ = OH | R ₄ = OH | |

- (7) R= H
(8) R= OH

- (10) R₃= H R₁= R₂=
(11) R₂= H R₁= R₃=
(12) R₂= R₃= H R₁=

(13) R=OCH₃
 (14) R=H

(27) R₁= OH R₂=H R₃= OCH₃ R₄=OH
 (28) R₁= OCH₃ R₂=OH R₃= H R₄=OH

Figure 3. Chemical structures of compounds found in green red and brown Brazilian propolis.

4. Antiparasitic activities of propolis

As said by Cable et al. (71), parasitic diseases are widely disseminated among human and animal populations, being responsible for serious negative impacts on these populations. It is now known that parasites maintain an intrinsic relationship with their hosts and the environment in which they live, being highly able to adapt and co-evolve with them when exposed to stress factors (71,72). Furthermore, parasitic diseases remain a major human health problem in poor areas in the tropics, caused by protozoa and helminths (73).

According to Almeida Vitor (74), protozoa are all protist and eukaryotic organisms formed by a single cell, divided into seven phyla of which only the phyla Sarcomastigophora, Apicomplexa, Ciliophora, Microspora are interested in human parasitology (**Table 2**). The following stand out in this phylum: *Plasmodium* sp. (malaria), *Trypanosoma* sp. (trypanosomiasis), *Leishmania* sp. (leishmaniasis), *Trichomonas* sp. (trichomoniasis), *Giardia* sp. (giardiasis), *Toxoplasma gondii* (toxoplasmosis) and *Entamoeba histolytica* (74).

Although the treatments against these protozoa have acceptable efficacy, some of these diseases have a limited number of therapeutic agents, as well as considerable side effects, as in the case of intestinal parasitosis (75), infections such as leishmaniasis and Chagas disease, they have limitations such as high cost, significant adverse effects, low adherence due to prolonged use, among other factors (76–78). One of the main barriers found in these treatments, would be the resistance potential presented by most of the available drugs, which was observed in several studies (78–81). Generally, the use of these therapeutic agents must be accompanied by monitoring to ensure their effectiveness (79,82).

"Helminths" is the technical name given to the parasitic worms belonging to the phylums Platyhelminthes (flatworms) and Nematoda (roundworms) being considered a serious public health problem (94). Most of these parasites affect poor areas with poor hygiene and sanitation conditions, affecting millions of people worldwide (**Table 2**). Among the parasitic diseases caused by helminths are schistosomiasis (*Schistosoma* sp.), echinococcosis or human hydatidosis (*Echinococcus* sp.), fascioliasis (*Fasciola* sp.), teniasis and cysticercosis (*Taenia solium*), filariasis (*Wuchereria bancrofti*, responsible for 90% of cases) and geo-helminths (*Ascaris lumbricoides*, *Trichuris trichiura*, *Necator americanus*, *Ancylostoma duodenale* and *Strongyloides stercoralis*).

Table 2. Global epidemiological situation of parasitic diseases and its treatments

Disease - Parasites	Number of infected cases worldwide	Number of deaths	Current treatments	References
Malaria -<i>Plasmodium</i> sp.	228 million ^[a]	405.000 ^[a]	Artemisinin-based combination therapies, Chloroquine	(83)
Chagas disease -<i>Trypanosoma cruzi</i>	>7 million	n.a.	Benznidazole, Nifurtimox	(84)
Visceral leishmaniasis - <i>Leishmania</i> sp.	± 300.000 ^[a]	>20.000 ^[a]		(85)
Cutaneous leishmaniasis - <i>Leishmania</i> sp.	1 million ^[b]	n.a.		(85)
Trichomoniasis - <i>Trichomonas vaginalis</i>	156 million	n.a.	Antibiotics	(86)
Schistosomiasis - <i>Schistosoma</i> sp.	>240 million	>200.000 ^[c]	Praziquantel	(87,88)
Echinococcosis (hydatid disease) - <i>Echinococcus</i> sp.	>1 million	n.a.	PAIR ^[d] technique	(89)
Taeniasis - <i>Taenia solium</i>	2.8 million ^[e]	n.a.	Praziquantel, Niclosamide, Albendazole	(90)
Fascioliasis -<i>Fasciola</i> sp.	2.4 million	n.a.	Triclabendazole	(91)
Lymphatic filariasis - <i>Wuchereria bancrofti</i>	± 40 million	n.a.	Albendazole, Ivermectin	(92)
Soil-transmitted helminth infections - <i>Ascaris lumbricoides</i>, <i>Trichuris trichiura</i>, <i>Necator americanus</i>, <i>Ancylostoma duodenale</i> and <i>Strongyloides stercoralis</i>	>1.5 billion	n.a.	Albendazole, Ivermectin, Mebendazole	(93)

^[a] Last reported in 2018. ^[b] In the last 5 years. ^[c] Only in sub-Saharan Africa. ^[d] Surgical technique involving puncture, aspiration, injection, re-aspiration. ^[e] Disability-adjusted life-years (DALYs) in 2015. n.a.: data not available.

Mass anti-helminthic drug administrations (MDA) remains the primary control program against *Schistosoma* sp. and soil-transmitted helminthiases. Despite the accompanying achievements with this program, the MDA unfortunately does not prevent a reinfection of individuals living in endemic areas, since there is no stimulation of the acquired immunity, for which a vaccine is necessary (95). However, until now, there is no vaccine capable of acting against these parasites (96). In addition, the growing increase in the number of reports on parasites resistant to their treatments combined with the absence of new treatment programs for such parasites becomes a major challenge in view of the harmful impact of these organisms on public health. (95,97).

4.1 Helminths

Table 3. Antiparasitic activity of several propolis samples against helminths

Propolis (source)	Parasite	Dose	Activity	References
Helminths				
Turkey propolis (Anzer-Rize) (ethanolic extract)	<i>Echinococcus granulosus</i>	1µg/mL (<i>in vitro</i>)	Scolicidal activity against all protoscoleces after 3 minutes	(98)
Egyptian propolis (ethanolic extract)	<i>Fasciola gigantica</i>	10 µg/mL (<i>in vitro</i>)	Several ultrastructural damages of the suckers (oral and ventral) and tegument after 24 hours	(99)
Egyptian propolis (ethanolic extract)	<i>Schistosoma mansoni</i>	300 mg/kg/day for 4 weeks starting 49 days after infection (<i>in vivo</i>)	No anti-schistosomal activity when administered alone	(100)
Egyptian propolis	<i>Schistosoma mansoni</i>	250 mg/kg/day starting 5 days before infection and continued up to 45 days post infection (<i>in vivo</i>)	Reduction of 59.22% of the lung schistosomules and 58.38% of adult worms in immunosuppressed infected mice	(101)
Brazilian green propolis	<i>Schistosoma mansoni</i>	200, 100 and 50 µg/mL (<i>in vitro</i>)	Death of 100% of the worms after 24h (200 µg/mL). 86% of viability reduction after 72h and tegumental damages (100 µg/mL) Separation of all the parasite pairs after 24h (50 µg/mL) IC _{50/72h} : 36.60 µg/mL	(102)

Libyan propolis (ethanolic extracts)	<i>Trichinella spiralis</i>	1 µg/mL (<i>in vitro</i>)	Inhibition of viability (%) of 51.9 ± 0.1 to P3 sample and 59.3 ± 0.1 to P4 sample	(103)
		10 µg/mL (<i>in vitro</i>)	Inhibition of viability (%) of 63.6 ± 0.3 to P3 sample and 61.3 ± 0.7 to P4 sample	

4.1.1 *Echinococcus* sp.

Hydatidosis is a chronic parasitosis caused by the larvae of the cestode *Echinococcus granulosus*. The biggest concern around this disease is due to the formation of hydatid cysts into various tissues and organs of the host, and can only be removed through surgery or percutaneous aspiration, processes that do not nullify the risk of disruption of the hydatid cyst and release of prostoscoleces in adjacent tissues (104).

As presented in **Table 3**, the ethanolic extract of Turkish propolis demonstrated strong scolicide activity *in vitro*. Experiments of this same research group, in 2008, reported the action of this propolis on the liver and biliary tree of Wistar rats, demonstrating no side or pathological effects caused by propolis in the tissues involved (105).

4.1.2 *Fasciola* sp.

Fasciola sp. are trematodes founds mainly in cattle and sheeps, but that can accidentally infect humans, parasitizing bile ducts and causing an acute and chronic disease characterized by hepatomegaly, cholangitis and granulomas formation (106).

Safeguarding the antihelminthic potential of propolis, Hegazi and coworkers (99) demonstrated *in vitro* the activity of Egyptian propolis ethanolic extract (Siwa) on the tegument and suckers of *Fasciola gigantica* adult worms. After 24h of exposure of the parasites to different concentrations (10, 20 and 30 µg/mL) severe morphological damages occurred in these structures, from the formation of bubbles on the tegument surface to erosive and peeling processes with intense distortion of oral and ventral suckers.

Added to these results, tests conducted with three different types of Egyptian propolis (Siwa oasis, Matrooh beach and Dakahlia) indicated a potential inhibitory effect of propolis on *Fasciola gigantica* eggs, causing total inhibition of egg development and the death of the same ones at concentrations of 200 µg/mL (Siwa), 400 µg/mL (Matrooh) and 800 µg/mL (Dakahli) (107).

4.1.3 *Schistosoma* sp.

Affecting about 250 million people around the world, schistosomiasis is a parasitosis typical of poor communities in tropical and subtropical areas that lack adequate sanitation. Being caused by worms of the genus *Schistosoma*, the disease can, according to the species of the parasite, cause damage to various tissues and organs, such as liver, intestines and urogenital apparatus (88).

As shown in **Table 3**, the ethanolic extract of Egyptian propolis has no schistosomicidal activity *in vivo* when administered alone in mice infected with *Schistosoma mansoni*, the main species causing intestinal schistosomiasis. However, in this same study, Mahmoud et al. (100) when administering a combination of Praziquantel (standard treatment) and propolis achieved a significant reduction (98%) on parasitic burden in relation to the groups treated with these compounds alone. Noteworthy, in the groups treated only with propolis, a significant reduction in lymphocytic infiltrate can be noted, as well as in the number and diameter of granulomas.

Immunosuppressed mice undergoing prophylactic treatment (250 mg/kg/day, 5 days before infection and 45 days after infection) with Egyptian propolis showed significant reduction in the number of schistosomules in the lung and in the number of adult worms (**Table 3**), as well as a reduction in the amount of eggs in the feces, liver and intestine (61.8%, 49.9% and 45.8%, respectively) (101).

Trials conducted by our research group studied the effect of essential oils of *Baccharis dracunculifolia* (Bd-EO), botanical source of Brazilian green propolis, against adult worms of *S. mansoni*, pointing out its schistosomicidal effect *in vitro* by causing the death of all pairs of worms after 24 hours of incubation with Bd-EO at concentrations of 10, 50 and 100 µg/mL (108). Also, as recently published, the extract of Brazilian green propolis (Pex) when tested *in vitro* against adult worms of *S. mansoni* killed all the parasite at 200 µg/mL after 24 hours of incubation and, at 100 µg/mL significantly reduced the viability of the parasite (70% and 86% at 24h and 72h, respectively) with IC_{50/72h} value equal to 36.60 µg/mL (102). At this same study of our research group, Pex damaged the worm tegument with visible peeling of the tegument and formation of bubbles. Moreover, all the pairs of *S. mansoni* incubated with 100 and 50 µg/mL of Pex were separated in contrast with the negative control (102).

4.1.4 *Trichinella* sp.

A member of the order Trichurida, the nematode *Trichinella spiralis* can infect humans when they ingest meats contented encysted larvae of the parasite. The disease mainly affects muscle tissues (encysted larvae), causing severe pain and can lead to heart and lung damage.

Larvae, in turn, during systemic migration can cause nephritis, myocarditis, pneumonia and consequently the death of the host (109).

In the work of Siheri et al. (103), twelve samples of Lebanese propolis were tested against *T. spiralis*. Of these twelve, samples P6 to P12 did not present action against the parasite, on the other hand the samples P3 and P4 showed higher inhibitory activity at the lowest concentration (**Table 3**), while the samples P1, P2 and P5 obtained a percentage of inhibition > 50% of the worms only at the highest concentration.

4.1.5 *Caernohabditis elegans*

Although *Caernohabditis elegans* is a free-living helminth, it is a model organism for biological assays, being widely used in studies for the discovery of new anthelmintics (110,111). Salas and coworkers (112) investigated the nematicidal action of the ethanolic extract of Argentina propolis against the worm, obtaining a value of $IC_{50/24h} = 70 \mu\text{g/mL}$, while in studies conducted by Siheri et al. (103), lebanese propolis showed low activity against *C. elegans*, with low percentage of worm inhibition (<20% to $10 \mu\text{g/mL}$).

4.2 Protozoan

4.2.1 *Plasmodium* sp.

Being provoked by protozoas of the genus *Plasmodium* and transmitted by the bite of female mosquitoes of the genus *Anopheles*, malaria is today one of the most common parasite diseases (113). Data from the World Health Organization showed that in 2017 about 219 million cases of malaria with 435,000 deaths from it (83). One of the biggest concerns about this disease is the emergence of drug resistance used in the treatment of malaria (114), thus highlighting the needing for research and development of new drugs for treatment.

Safeguarding the antiplasmodic activity of propolis, Afrouzan et al. (115) tested four different fractions [70% ethanol (EtOH 70%), ethyl acetate (EA), hexane (n-Hex) and dichloromethane (DCM)] of Iranian propolis against *P. falciparum* 3D7 chloroquine strain (CQ)-sensitive (*in vitro*) and *P. berghei* (ANKA line) (*in vivo*). In the *in vitro* assays, EtOH 70% and DCM obtained the best results (**Table 4**) followed by the EA fraction ($IC_{50} = 37.65 \pm 7.23 \mu\text{g/mL}$) and low activity for n-Hex. In relation to *in vivo* studies, EtOH 70% and DCM showed a significant and dose-dependent reduction in the parasitic load of infected animals with *P. berghei* (ANKA strain) in relation to the control group (PBS), highlighting once again the antiplasmodic activity of EtOH70% after 14 days of infection with reductions of 65.1%, 66%

and 71% in parasitemia after treatment with 50-100 and 200 mg/kg of propolis, respectively (115).

Falcão et al. (116) studied *in vitro* the antiplasmodic action of phenolic propolis extracts from Portugal (**Table 4**) and their floral sources [male (PM) and female (PF) species of *Populus x Canadensis* Moenchen and *Cistus ladanifer* L.], highlighting the antiplasmodic activity of phenolic extract PM with IC₅₀ = 10.90 µg/mL.

The Saudi propolis, when tested *in vivo* against *P. chabaudi* demonstrated antiplasmodic and splenoprotective action (117), with parasitemic reductions between 49% and 70% (**Table 4**) and restoration of the spleen, which recover much of its normal aspect, observing absence of vacuolization and restoration of the splenic capsule in the treatment with 100 mg/kg of propolis.

Another important data refers to the trials performed with *Baccharis dracunculifolia*, botanical source of Brazilian green propolis. *In vitro* assays performed by Silva Filho et al. (118) with the crude extract of this plant (BdE) and its isolates against *P. falciparum* clones [Sierra Leone D6 (chloroquine-sensitive) and Indochina W2 (chloroquine-resistant)] presented IC₅₀ values equal to 25 µg/mL and 13 µg/mL, respectively. In the same study, the crude extract of Brazilian green propolis was evaluated, with IC₅₀ values equal to 20 µg/mL (D6 clone) and 13 µg/mL (W2 clone). On the other hand, antiplasmodic experiments carried out *in vitro* by Parreira et al. (108) with the essential oil of *B. dracunculifolia* showed no activity against these same strains.

Table 4. Antiparasitic activity of several propolis samples against protozoas

Propolis (source)	Parasite	Dose	Activity	References
Protozoa				
Iranian propolis (Morad Beyg) (EtOH 70% or DCM)	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> 3D7 [chloroquine (CQ)-sensitive]	6,25 to 400 µg/mL (<i>in vitro</i>)	IC ₅₀ values of 16.2 ± 2.9 to dichloromethane and 27.0 ± 2.2 to ethanol 70% extracts	(115)
Iranian propolis (Morad Beyg) (EtOH 70% or DCM)	CQ-sensitive <i>Plasmodium berghei</i> (ANKA strain)	100 and 200 mg/kg/day for 14 days (<i>in vivo</i>)	EtOH 70%: 66% and 71% of suppression of parasitemia, respectively DCM: 62% and 65% of suppression of parasitemia, respectively	(115)
Portuguese propolis (Bragança and Leiria countries)	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> GHA-strain	20 mg/mL (<i>in vitro</i>)	IC ₅₀ values of 30.1 ± 4.1 to Bragança sample and 8.8 ± 1.8 to Leiria sample	(116)
Saudi propolis (methanolic extract)	<i>Plasmodium chabaudi</i>	25, 50 and 100 mg/kg for 7 days (<i>in vivo</i>)	49%, 52% and 70% of suppression of parasitemia, respectively	(117)

Brazilian propolis (Lageado Farm) (ethanolic extract)	<i>Giardia duodenalis</i> BTU-10 strain	7.81 to 500 mg/ml (<i>in vitro</i>)	500 mg/ml inhibited growth by 95% after a 96h incubation	(119)
Mexican propolis (Sonora region) (methanolic extracts)	<i>Giardia lamblia</i>	25 to 200 µg/mL (<i>in vitro</i>)	Inhibition of trophozoite growth from Ures sample with IC ₅₀ value of 63.8 ± 7.1 µg/mL	(120)
Yellow cuban propolis (methanolic extract)	<i>Trichomonas vaginalis</i> isolate C173	1.6 to 200 µg/mL (<i>in vitro</i>)	IC ₅₀ values equal to 3.7 ± 0.7 to YCP-2 and 3.2 ± 0.1 to YCP-48 samples	(121)
Brazilian brown propolis (Minas Gerais-MG and Mato Grosso do Sul -MS) (ethanolic extracts)	<i>Trichomonas vaginalis</i> isolate ATCC 30236	500 µg/mL (<i>in vitro</i>)	Trophozoites viability (%) equal to 0.62 ± 0.43 to P-Et/MG and 0.00 ± 0.00 to P-Et/MS samples	(122)
Brazilian red propolis (essential oil)	<i>Trichomonas vaginalis</i> isolate 30236	25 to 500 µg/mL (<i>in vitro</i>)	100% death of trophozoites at 500 µg/mL and IC ₅₀ value of 100 µg/mL	(123)
Egyptian propolis (ethanolic and water extracts)	<i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	50 mg/kg 3 days before infection and then administered again the same dose on the 5th dpi for 7 successive days (<i>in vivo</i>)	EEP: 88% of reduction of oocysts shedding at 4 th dpi WEP: 91% of reduction of oocysts shedding at the 6 th dpi	(124)
Brazilian red propolis (ethanolic extract)	<i>Trypanosoma cruzi</i> (Y strain)	75 mg/mL and 300 mg/mL (<i>in vitro</i>)	More than 90% of inhibition of growth in 24 h of incubation	(125)
Brazilian red propolis (hydroethanolic extract)	<i>Trypanosoma cruzi</i> CL-B5	15.62 to 1000 µg/mL (<i>in vitro</i>)	IC ₅₀ < 31 µg/mL to sample from Pernambuco	(126)
Brazilian green propolis	<i>Trypanosoma cruzi</i> (Y strain)	3 to 1000 µg/mL (<i>in vitro</i>)	Values of IC ₅₀ (µg/mL): Extracellular amastigotes: 18.7 ± 3.2 (first day of treatment) Intracellular amastigotes: 8.5 ± 1.8 (4 th day of treatment) Epimastigotes: 149.0 ± 4.6 (4 th day of treatment)	(127)
Brazilian green propolis	<i>Trypanosoma cruzi</i> (Y strain)	300 mg/kg for 10 consecutive days beginning on first day post infection (<i>in vivo</i>)	Parasitemia peak (parasites mL ⁻¹ (×10 ⁻⁴)): Untreated group: 558.2 ± 209.7 Treated (300mg/kg): 227.7 ± 33.4	(127)
Nigerian red propolis	<i>Trypanosoma brucei</i> (Lister strain 427)	20 µg/ml (<i>in vitro</i>)	EC ₅₀ : 4.2 ± 0.04 µg/mL	(128)
	<i>Trypanosoma brucei</i> (B48 clone)	20 µg/ml	EC ₅₀ : 3.9 ± 0.16 µg/mL	

		(<i>in vitro</i>)		
	<i>Trypanosoma brucei</i> (aqp2/aqp3 null strain)	20 µg/ml (<i>in vitro</i>)	EC ₅₀ : 4.4 ± 0.26 µg/mL	
Propolis (Sigma Chemical Co., lot No. 88F0369) (ethanolic and dimethylsulphoxide extracts)	<i>Trypanosoma cruzi</i> (Y strain)	12.5 to 250 µg/mL (<i>in vitro</i>)	ID _{50/48h} values (µg/mL): Amastigotes EEP: 41.4 ± 2.9 DEP: 140.0 ± 25.4 Epimastigotes EEP: 72.5 ± 15.0 DEP: 67.4 ± 3.1	(129)
Propolis (Sigma Chemical Co., lot No. 88F0369) (ethanolic and dimethylsulphoxide extracts)	<i>Trypanosoma cruzi</i> (Y strain)	200 and 400 mg/kg for 10 days (<i>in vivo</i>)	No alteration on the parasitemia and mortality levels	(130)
European propolis (different countries) (ethanolic extracts)	<i>Trypanosoma brucei</i> (Lister 427WT strain)	20 µg/ml (<i>in vitro</i>)	EC ₅₀ : 3.67 ± 0.30 µg/mL (Norfolk 3, UK)	(131)
	<i>Trypanosoma brucei</i> (B48 clone)	20 µg/ml (<i>in vitro</i>)	EC ₅₀ : 2.5 ± 0.14 µg/mL (Norfolk 3, UK)	
	<i>Trypanosoma congolense</i> (IL3000 strain Savannah-type)	20 µg/ml (<i>in vitro</i>)	EC ₅₀ : 1.96 ± 1.01 µg/mL (Bulgaria 3)	
Portuguese propolis (Bragança and Leiria countries)	<i>Trypanosoma brucei</i> (Squib-427 strain, suramin-sensitive)	20 mg/mL (<i>in vitro</i>)	IC ₅₀ values of 1.7 ± 0.5 to Bragança and 3.8 ± 1.2 to Leiria samples	(116)
	<i>Trypanosoma cruzi</i> (Tulahuen CL2 strain, nifurtimox-sensitive)	20 mg/mL (<i>in vitro</i>)	IC ₅₀ values of 6.2 ± 1.9 to Bragança and 7.7 ± 2.1 to Leiria samples	
Brazilian propolis (different regions) (ethanolic extracts)	<i>Trypanosoma cruzi</i> (Y strain)		ED _{50/24h} (µg/ml) equal to 421.0 ± 26.5 to 136-Et100 sample	(132)
Bulgarian propolis (ethanolic extract)	<i>Trypanosoma cruzi</i> (Y strain)	25 and 50 mg/kg for 14 days after infection (<i>in vivo</i>)	Parasitemia peak (10 ⁴ par/mL) Control: 840.2 ± 271.6 25 mg/kg: 580.6 ± 327.8 50mg/kg: 428.0 ± 248.9	(133)
Brazilian propolis (Minas Gerais, MG) (hydroalcoholic extract)	<i>Leishmania (Viannia) braziliensis</i>	1 to 750 µg/ml (<i>in vitro</i>) 1,5 mg/kg for 3 months (<i>in vivo</i>)	IC _{50/24h} of 18.13 µg/mL <i>In vivo</i> : EBP oral: 78.6% 78.6% injury reduction	(134)

			EPB topic: 84.3% injury reduction EPB oral+topic: 90% injury reduction	
Ecuadorian propolis (Quito, Guayaquil e Cotacachi)	<i>Leishmania (Leishmania) amazonensis</i>	12,5 to 200 µg/ml (<i>in vitro</i>)	Promastigote: IC _{50/72h} of 55.4 ± 2 µg/mL to QPS, 27.5 ± 4.7 µg/mL to CPS and 141.7 ± 4.8 µg/mL Amastigote: IC _{50/48h} of 17.9 ± 1.7 µg/mL to CPS	(135)
Brazilian propolis (Pernambuco and Alagoas)	<i>Leishmania (Viannia) braziliensis, Leishmania infantum</i>		Promastigote: IC _{50/72h} of 35.22 to RP-PER, 42.29 to RP-PED, 55.79 to RP-AL and 90.46 µg/mL to DER for <i>L. (V.) braziliensis</i> . IC _{50/72h} of 37.45 to RP-PER, 200.66 to RP-PED, 109.49 to RP-AL and 134.56 µg/mL to DER for <i>L. infantum</i> .	(136)
Brazilian red propolis (Alagoas) (ethanolic extract)	<i>Leishmania (Viannia) braziliensis</i>	5 to 1000 µg/mL (<i>in vitro</i>)	IC _{50/24h} of 37.9 to EEP, 1.34 to NRPE, 47.23 to NRPEA2, 154.2 to NRPEA3 and 193.2 µg/mL to NRPEA4	(137)
Brazilian red propolis (Alagoas) (ethanolic extract)	<i>Leishmania (Leishmania) amazonensis</i>	27 mg/Sb ⁺⁵ /kg/day, topically propolis, for 20 days (<i>in vivo</i>)	Amastigote: Gluca + HBO: 2.1 ± 0.32 vs. 5.9 ± 0.9 Gluca: 3.9 ± 0.7 HBO: 4.2 ± 0.6 <i>In vivo</i> : Gluca + HBO: injury not increased Gluca + propolis: prevented the appearance of the lesion HBO: similar to untreated control Gluca: prevented injury growth Propolis: increased injury	(138)
Bolivian propolis (methanol extract)	<i>Leishmania (Viannia) braziliensis, Leishmania (Leishmania) amazonensis</i>	1 to 100 µg/mL (<i>in vitro</i>)	<i>L. braziliensis</i> : Chapare: 10.9 ± 0.8 San Andres 2: 7.8 ± 1.1 <i>L. amazonensis</i> : Valle alto: 9.7 ± 1.1 Chapare: 8.0 ± 0.8	(139)
Brazilian green and red propolis (Paraná, Minas Gerais, Alagoas) (ethanolic extract)	<i>Leishmania (Leishmania) amazonensis</i>	3 to 100 µg/mL (<i>in vitro</i>)	Amastigote: BRG/BRPG/BRV/BRP: significant reduction of both the percentage of infection and number of intracellular parasites Promastigote: Dose-dependent effect	(140)

Brazilian green, brown and red propolis (Bahia) (ethanolic extract)	<i>Leishmania (Viannia) braziliensis</i>	10 to 100 µg/mL (<i>in vitro</i>)	Amastigote: reduction of parasitic load in a dose-dependent manner	(141)
Brazilian propolis	<i>Leishmania (Leishmania) amazonensis</i>	5 mg/kg for 30 days (<i>in vivo</i>)	Prevented the growth of promastigotes using 100 µg/mL for 24h The proliferation decreased in all concentrations after 96 and 168h	(142)
Brazilian green propolis	<i>Leishmania (Viannia) braziliensis</i>	5 to 100 µg/mL (<i>in vitro</i>)	Oral WEP - Significant reduction of parasites in the liver (44%)	(143)
Brazilian green propolis (aqueous extract)	<i>Leishmania infantum C43</i> (wild strain)	30 and 500 mg/kg for 2 weeks (<i>in vivo</i>)	Single dose of liposomal MA - reduced parasite loads in the liver and spleen by 41 % Oral treatment with WEP associated with a single dose of liposomal MA - reduced the parasitic load both in the liver and spleen in the same level observed with treatment with liposomal MA (40 and 30%, respectively)	(144)

4.2.2 *Giardia* sp.

Caused by the parasite *Giardia lamblia* (synonyms *Giardia intestinalis* and *Giardia duodenalis*), giardiasis is an intestinal disease marked mainly by the syndrome of malabsorption and constant diarrhea (145), being today considered one of the most common intestinal parasites in humans (146).

Clinical trials conducted in Cuba at 1988, by Miyares et al. (147), showed the giardicide potential of propolis in children and adults. For 5 days, children were treated with 10% of propolis, a propolis-based preparation and adults with 20% and 30% of the preparation. In this trial, cure rates of 52% can be observed for children and, for adults, 40% and 60% in treatments with 20% and 30% of propolis, respectively.

Nuñez et al. (145) found similar giardicide propolis activity in a clinical trial conducted with 256 children infected with *G. lamblia* receiving treatment with 30% of propolis for 10 or 20 days. After the twentieth day there was a cure rate of 79.8%, a value similar to the treatment with metronidazole (79.3%), thus indicating a relevant giardicide activity of propolis.

Besides provoking the *in vitro* growth inhibition of *Giardia* trophozoites (**Table 4**), Ures propolis (Sonora, Mexico) caused morphological damages in trophozoites incubated for 48 h with 200 µg/mL, observing swollen parasites with slow movements (120). In this same study, seasonal samples of this propolis were collected, highlighting the activity of the sample collected during the summer ($IC_{50} = 23.8 \pm 2.3$ µg/mL).

In vitro growth inhibition of this parasite was also confirmed by Freitas et. al., (119) (**Table 4**) in his work with Brazilian propolis, which was also able to reduce the adhesion capacity of trophozoites (67.9% and 69.5% in 250 and 500 µg/mL, respectively).

4.2.3 *Trichomonas vaginalis*

Among the sexually transmitted non-viral diseases is trichomoniasis, caused by the flagellate protozoa *Trichomonas vaginalis* (148). According to Neves et al. (149), this parasitosis is responsible for cases of infertility, premature births, cervical and prostate cancer, as well as favors the transmission of the HIV virus.

In 1976, Starzyk et al. (150), demonstrated that 150 µg/mL of ethanolic extract of propolis exerts lethal effect on three *T. vaginalis* strains. Corroborating these data, Xu & Shi (151) presented promising results of *in vitro* tricomonicide activity, with parasite survival rates equal to 3% and 0% after 24 hours of incubation with propolis under concentrations of 3.84 and 7.68 (mg/ml), respectively.

Among 18 samples of Cuban propolis tested by Fidalgo et al. (121), two samples of yellow propolis (YCP - **Table 4**), one sample of brown propolis (BCP1 - $IC_{50} = 6.2 \pm 0.3$ µg/mL) and one of red propolis (RCP29 - $IC_{50} = 8.9 \pm 0.1$ µg/mL) were able to inhibit the growth of parasites.

Experiments performed with essential oils extracted from the Brazilian red propolis (EOP) against trophozoites of isolate 30236 of *T. vaginalis* corroborates the tricomonicide action of propolis (123). After 24h of incubation with 500 µg/mL of EOP, a 100% reduction in the viability of trophozoites was obtained, presenting a IC_{50} value equal to 100 µg/mL. In this same concentration, after 12h, the growth of parasites was reduced by 36%, with total death after 24 h of exposure to EOP.

4.2.4 *Cryptosporidium* sp.

Cryptosporidium are intracellular protozoan parasites that develop, preferably, in the microvilli of the epithelial cells of the gastrointestinal tract of their hosts, being transmitted by ingestion or inhalation of oocysts, as well as by self-infection. Symptoms are characterized by

watery diarrhea, abdominal pain, anorexia, vomiting, dehydration, being more severe in children and immunocompetent individuals (152).

Besides the reduction in the release of *Cryptosporidium* oocysts by mice prophylactically treated with ethanolic (EEP) and water (WEP) extracts of Egyptian propolis (**Table 4**), Soufy et al. (124) also noticed a reduction of 89% and 75% of oocysts at the end of the seventh day of therapeutic treatment with 50 mg/kg of EEP and WEP, respectively.

4.2.5 *Trypanosoma* sp.

Reaching Africa and Central and South America, trypanosomiasis is an acute and chronic disease caused by flagellate protozoa of the genus *Trypanosoma*. In the Americas, parasitosis is known as Chagas disease, being transmitted through the feces of triatomine bugs infected with *T. cruzi* or by oral form when the insect is crushed along with food products such as sugarcane and açai. The disease is characterized by severe and progressive damage to the myocardium and gastrointestinal tract (153). In Africa, transmission of parasitosis occurs through the bite of the Tse-Tse fly infected with the species *T. brucei gambiense* or *T. brucei rhodesiense*, generating strong accesses of severe headache, insomnia, enlarged lymph nodes, anemia, rash and changes in the central nervous system (153).

Experiments carried out by Silva et al. (125) with samples of Brazilian propolis (green, red and brown) obtained *in vitro* a high percentage of proliferation inhibition of parasites (**Table 4**), highlighting the highest percentage of inhibition for red propolis (98% after 24h). On the other hand, in this same study, it was observed that there was a decrease in inhibition of parasite proliferation between 24h and 96h of incubation with the samples of green and brown propolis.

Morphological changes in epimastigotes and trypomastigotes were noted by De Castro et al. (127) after 24h incubation of parasites in different concentrations of Brazilian green propolis. Mitochondrial swollen, shortening and rounding of the body of epimastigotes were perceived in 100 µg/mL, 250 µg/mL and 300 µg/mL. For trypomastigotes, treated at concentrations lower than the value of IC₅₀ (66.2 ± 3.7 µg/mL), the formation of blisters that led to irregular expansion of the body and flagellar membranes of the parasites was observed.

Compounds isolated from Lebanese propolis exhibited significant activity against *T. brucei* (s427) and *T. brucei* (B48)(103). Among the 10 compounds tested, 4 presented better activities, highlighting cardol plus mangiferolic acid with EC₅₀ values (µg/mL) equal to 0.70 ± 0.03 (s427) and 0.70 ± 0.06 (B48), followed by demethylpiperitol: 2.7 ± 0.2 (s427) and 2.68 ± 0.04 (B48), isocupressic acid: 3.0 ± 0.1 (s427) and 2.73 ± 0.11 (B48) and cycloartanol: 3.7 ± 0.1 (s427) and 3.42 ± 0.08 (B48)(103).

In 2004, Filho et al. (154) tested the *in vitro* tripanocidal activity for different extracts of *Baccharis dracunculifolia* and its isolates. The ethanolic extracts of the branches and leaves of the plant obtained 100% lysis of the trypomastigote forms of the parasite, a result that was repeated for the dichloromethane fraction of the leaf extract. Among the compounds, isolate 1 and 3 showed better trypanocidal activity, smoothing about 98% of the parasites and with IC₅₀ values equal to 247.6 ± 1.13 and 249.8 ± 1.02 µg/mL, respectively.

4.2.6 *Leishmania* sp.

The leishmaniasis are complex diseases of the tropical areas of the world, caused by protozoa of the genus *Leishmania* and disseminated by infected female phlebotomine sandflies, leading to a wide spectrum of clinical forms that can be clearly observed as: cutaneous (CL), mucocutaneous (MCL) or visceral (VL) (135,136).

In the work of Machado et al., 2007 (137) was presented the *in vitro* activity of three ethanolic extracts of Brazilian propolis against *L. amazonensis*, *L. braziliensis*, *L. infantum* and *L. major*. A greater effect of Et-Blg was observed for *L. amazonensis* and *L. major* (**Table 4**). For *L. braziliensis* Et-Bra was about three times more active, suggesting that other phenolic compounds, besides flavonoids and also amines, are probably the compounds involved in leishmanicide activity.

Regueira-Neto et al. (2018) (107), analyzed extracts from different regions of Ecuador and Brazil, in *Leishmania* species. When comparing the leishmanicide activity of the three red propolis samples used in the study, it was observed that promastigote forms of *L. braziliensis* were more susceptible to all extracts than *L. infantum* (**Table 4**).

The potential of red propolis extract incorporated in polymeric nanoparticles was explored by Nascimento et al., (2016) (117) in order to evaluate its antioxidant and leishmanicide activity. The leishmanicide activity of the nanoparticles was not found to be a concentration-dependent response, but is related to the encapsulation efficiency and the ratio between polymer matrix and red propolis extract present in the nanoparticles. The composition of NRPE A4 showed the lowest amount of EEP and showed the lowest leishmania activity (**Table 4**).

In a similar study to Nascimento et al., (2016) (117), infected mice were treated for 14 days (PBS, MA, empty liposomes, MA encapsulated in liposomes, WEP, WEP + MA association and WEP + Lipo MA association). Oral treatment with WEP for 14 days caused a significant reduction of parasites in the liver (44%), such effect was not observed in the spleen. Oral treatment with WEP associated with a single dose of liposomal MA reduced the parasitic load

in the liver and spleen at the same level observed in the treatment with liposomal MA (40 and 30%, respectively) (124).

According to Miranda and coworkers (2015) (122), the lesions in all treated groups (glucantime, propolis, RuNO and Propolis + RuNO), showed a significantly slower development compared to the infected control. On day 30, the mean lesion size was 8.75 ± 1.32 mm in the propolis treated group, 8.20 ± 1.13 mm with RuNO, 8.91 ± 1.03 mm with RuNO + propolis and 8.10 ± 1.01 mm with Glucantime. Regarding the efficacy of treatments in the parasitic load, was observed a marked reduction in the number of *L. amazonensis* at the site of the lesion in all groups treated, with no difference between them.

5. Future perspectives

Studies with propolis, a resinous bee product rich in bioactive compounds, have demonstrated its antiparasitic potential as can be addressed in this review. However, some gaps remain unfilled, making room for some questions: (a) what is the cytotoxicity of propolis in front of host cells? (b) what is the best range of concentrations to be used in *in vitro* assays? (c) what are the mechanisms of action of propolis in the various parasitic diseases? (d) the *in vivo* effect is due to antiparasitic or immunomodulatory activity? (e) since seasonality implies changes in the chemical profile of propolis, what is the need for a standardization of extracts? (f) extract, isolated compounds, combination... what is the best option to be used?

(a) Although the cytotoxic activity of propolis against tumor cells is well described (155), the safety of using propolis in some mammalian cell lines is necessary regarding the maximum concentrations and dosages to be used. Data in the literature indicate that in low concentrations, propolis has no toxic effect *in vitro* (134,135). When analyzing the cytotoxic effect of dry, alcoholic and glycolic extracts of propolis, on the viability of human and murine macrophages, Rebouças-Silva and collaborators (156), observed that cell viability was not affected by each tested concentration (10, 50 and 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) after 48 hours of treatment. In contrast, Ayres et al., 2007 (140), in analyzes with ethanol extracts of Brazilian green propolis, collected in Paraná, found that in concentrations above 25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ the extracts were toxic to macrophages, as well as in the study by Dantas et al., 2006 (157). On the other hand, the red propolis extracts collected in Minas Gerais and Alagoas, were not toxic to macrophages and inhibited the intracellular proliferation of *L. amazonensis*. Alagoas extract was the most active and the treatment of macrophages did not lead to morphological changes assessed by light microscopy (140).

(b) Specific criteria are proposed to define correct answers and clues in the development of drugs for infectious diseases (158,159), however in most cases, more detailed biological and/or pharmacokinetic studies are necessary to align strategies according to specific targets (159). In this sense, it is necessary, analyzes that guarantee not only the efficacy against pathogens, but also the individual's safety, with that the selectivity index is a relevant factor in the different studies. As reported in the work by Amarante et al. 2012 (160), no effect on cell viability was detected for concentrations of propolis up to 50 µg/ml, as in studies by González-Búrguez 2018 (161). In addition to these studies, Búfalo et al., (25), also reports, according to the immunomodulatory action of propolis, the activation of macrophages, as well as their growth in culture after the administration of propolis (134,162). Therefore, the variability in concentrations can be attributed to several factors: the use of different cell lines, the place of origin of propolis and, therefore, its composition, the times determined for each treatment and the type of propolis extract (liquid or ethanolic) (161).

(c - d) The mechanisms of action by which propolis acts on parasites remain unclear. On the other hand, the immunomodulatory activity of propolis is strongly described in numerous studies found in the literature (24,25,134,160,163) as one of the important mechanisms of its action in different parasites, however, due to the great diversity of climate, soil, location and phytogeographic characteristics of the collection site and the time of collection, are factors that directly influence the physical and chemical properties of the different types of propolis (136,141). These factors make standardizing propolis difficult (5). *In vitro*, propolis can act directly on microorganisms and *in vivo* stimulate the immune system, activating the mechanisms involved in the death of the microorganism (160). In the study of Salomão et al. 2011 (127), extracts of Brazilian green propolis and Bulgarian propolis were evaluated in the infective forms of *T. cruzi*, *in vitro* and *in vivo*, where an increase in the accumulation of lipids and less electron density was observed matrix in reservoirs, which are crucial for the storage of lipids and proteins in epimastigotes (164), together with the decrease in acridine orange fluorescence and structural changes in the Golgi Complex, suggesting that the ethanol extract of Brazilian green propolis interferes with endocytic pathway. The reduction in electron density by propolis may be due to a lower content of proteins, essential for the metacyclogenesis of trypomastigotes (165). Other *in vitro* studies with protozoa of the genus *Leishmania* report that nitric oxide donors can inhibit mitochondrial respiration in amastigotes and promastigotes of *Leishmania* spp., Leading to the death of the parasite (142,166). Despite these studies, it cannot

be said that this is the mechanism by which antiparasitic action occurs, strengthening the need for further research in order to understand the ways in which propolis acts on the host organism and on the parasite itself.

(e) Another important factor is the chemical composition of propolis, which is strongly influenced by seasonality and botanical origin, a condition that directly interferes with its biological activity. As observed in the work of Alday-Provencio et al. (120), samples of propolis obtained during the seasons showed different levels in the biological activity against *G. lamblia* trophozoites, highlighting the sample collected in the summer ($IC_{50} = 23.8 \pm 2.3 \mu\text{g/mL}$). This condition is strengthened in the study by Regueira-Neto et al. (126) when they pointed out that the samples of Brazilian red propolis collected in the rainy season had a better leishmanicidal and trypanomicidal activity ($IC_{50} = 35.22$ and $< 31 \mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively) than samples collected in the dry period ($IC_{50} = 42.29$ and $54.86 \mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively). Regarding the botanical source, Falcão et al. (116) evaluated the anti-protozoan potential of botanical sources of European propolis (*Populus x Canadensis* Moenchen, male species - PM and female - PF; *Cistus ladanifer* L.), demonstrating again different potentials for each species. While PM and PF obtained similar results for *L. infantum*, *T. cruzi* and *T. brucei*; PM, in turn, was more active against *P. falciparum* ($IC_{50} = 10.9 \mu\text{g/mL}$) than PF ($IC_{50} = 28.5 \mu\text{g/mL}$), while the sample of *C. ladanifer* L. was more effective against *T. brucei* ($IC_{50} = 2.0 \mu\text{g/mL}$).

(f) When analyzing the various strategic possibilities, related to the development of new molecules active against different infectious diseases, one must take into account the reports of resistance to available drugs and especially the specific targets to be reached, in order that such molecules are effective, safe and accessible for the treatment of parasitic diseases (28,80,159). In this sense, the use of substances isolated from natural products, extracts, combination of new molecules with existing drugs or even the repositioning of drugs, requires from researchers several analyzes of targets, as well as analyzes of mechanism of action, pharmacokinetics, cytotoxicity, as well as as the possible escape mechanism of the different parasites (167,168). Isolated substances have specific chemical characteristics and in some cases with a known mechanism of action, as in the case of flavonoids, diterpenes, terpenes, quinones, chalcones, among others (169). However, although there are a large number of publications related to chemical and biological studies, many samples of propolis still remain unexplored (51). Some studies describe the great potential of propolis extracts due to a combination of their

immunostimulatory, antibacterial and anti-inflammatory activities, thus being able to potentiate their effect when compared to isolated substances (134).

6. Conclusion

Although the mechanisms of action of propolis are little known, its antiparasitic activity against some protozoa and helminths is undeniable. As discussed in this review, propolis is a promising natural product for more detailed studies in the field of parasitology, a medical area that needs attention and has already been presenting problems with its current treatments. However, due to the great chemical diversity of propolis around the globe, it is necessary to standardize this product so that research can converge in the future, thus reducing the discrepancies between the works.

7. References

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